

CoARA Action Plan Dublin City University

Introduction

DCU joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) in 2022. As a signatory of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) that underpins the Coalition, DCU commits to sharing how we engage with the objectives and commitments therein, including an action plan with defined milestones which is contained in this document. In DCU, work in advancing research assessment is approached under the umbrella of Open Research and is overseen by the DCU Open Research Steering Group, established in May 2022.

The Steering Group is a university-wide group with senior representatives from all five faculties as well as DCU Research Support Services, DCU Library, DCU People (HR), DCU Communications, Marketing and Events and DCU Digital Technology Solutions. It leads the University's implementation of the National Open Research Forum (NORF) Action Plan 2022-30 and works more broadly to foster a culture of open research in DCU and to promote openness across the research lifecycle.

The DCU Open Research Steering Group's Implementation Plan identifies five key themes and focus areas. Two of these subgroups, *Incentives and Rewards* and *Policy and Governance*, directly relate to the topic of research assessment. The *Incentives and Rewards* subgroup includes representation from DCU People, our Human Resources unit, whose input is crucial to progressing and actualising many of the aims in this area. Across all these focus areas, the Implementation Plan aims

to ensure that “[Open research] principles become embedded across all institutional research assessment practice and processes”.

Policy and Strategy: In the DCU Strategy (2023-2028), Open Research is a key objective for the [Research](#) pillar and includes the aims to; “support, encourage, incentivise and provide training for broad open research practices” and “Build a strengthened research culture consistent with the CoARA principles.” The [DCU Code of Good Research Practice](#) further expands that “as a key component of creating a research environment conducive to good research practice, DCU has committed to implementing the principles of responsible research and to the open, transparent and responsible use of research metrics.”

In 2021 DCU launched a [Statement on Responsible Use of Research Metrics](#) at DCU, setting out seven guiding principles for those using research metrics for assessment purposes to ensure a nuanced and balanced approach:

1. Be open, transparent and explicit about the criteria used to assess research performance in the University.
2. Ensure research metrics will be used to support but not supplant qualitative expert judgement and review.
3. Refrain from the use of venue-based metrics, such as JIF, in assessing the merits of a particular research output.
4. Ensure recruitment/promotion processes assess candidates across multiple research performance indicators. Clear guidelines on assessment procedures and criteria will be provided to candidates and reviewers.
5. Take into account disciplinary diversity in research output types (examples include, where relevant for each discipline, journal articles, monographs, edited collections, creative works, datasets, software, commissioned reports and in languages other than English).
6. Recognise research contributions in the form of impacts on wider society (e.g. citation in policy).
7. Ensure that assessment of performance at an individual level fully takes into consideration the circumstances of an individuals’ career path (e.g. maternity leave, career break etc.) specifically incorporating principles enshrined in DCU Equality, Diversity & Inclusion Policies.

The [DCU Open Research website](#) includes a section on [Responsible Metrics](#) with a link to the statement above, along with International frameworks and initiatives including CoARA. Other frameworks included there and used as reference points in the work of the Steering Group are DORA and the Leiden Manifesto. Information about CoARA and responsible research assessment are included in training on Open Research for researchers to foster awareness across the University. Training and consultation on traditional metrics tools such as Scival are always framed in this wider context of responsible use of metrics.

The current [DCU Strategic Plan](#), including the research component, is a living strategic plan in keeping with the rapidly changing research and economic environment. This CoARA Action Plan includes actions aligned with the strategic plan and associated implementation periods until 2028 while being agile and flexible allowing for changing contexts and environments. As highlighted in this plan, DCU is already implementing many of the CoARA commitments, while other opportunities have arisen through the work of the Open Research Steering Group. We undertake an annual review of actions in this plan to (a) update progress for existing actions and (b) to ensure new opportunities or emerging practices can continue to be identified and actioned appropriately.

Action Plan

	CoARA Commitments	Action
1	Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	Appraise all individual research assessment processes, including promotion, recruitment, and other institutional awards and recognitions of research impact, identifying specific areas for further discussion or engagement to align with CoARA commitments and/or DCU Statement on Responsible Use of Research Metrics (RURM). Review all policies and statements to make explicit our engagement with CoARA and the requirements of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, being cognisant of the needs and nature of the research and the career stage from Masters to Doctoral to Postdoctoral level and beyond.
2	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported	Explore development of internal peer review processes for research related assessments and evaluation processes.

	by responsible use of quantitative indicators	Develop discipline-specific training around peer review and quality assessment, including guidance on Open Peer Review and Narrative CVs in Open Research training offerings.
3	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	Align and promote all documentation in relation to appointments and career progression with CoARA and DCU Statement on Responsible Use of Metrics (RURM) and develop guidance and training for interview chairs, panels and line managers.
4	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment	Ensure that DCU communications and strategy around Institutional rankings are not conflated with individual researcher assessment and that DCU internal communications raises awareness on the limitations of rankings.
5	Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to	Continue to utilise the DCU Open Research Steering Group structure to advocate for resourcing of Open Research and Responsible Research Assessment at all levels.
6	Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes	<p>Also see: review of promotion and assessment criteria outlined under Commitment 1</p> <p>Explore CRIS and other systems' capacity to gather and share diverse types of academic contribution to research and knowledge exchange. Identify where and how such data could be fed into university processes relating to research assessment.</p> <p>Continue to monitor and review internal promotion, probation, and appraisal criteria to ensure they meet the DCU Statement on Responsible Use of Metrics (RURM). Develop criteria, tools and processes together with researchers (co-create) in different disciplines and at different career stages considering gender balance and diversity; enabling recognition of the diversity of research activities and practices that contribute to research quality, including diverse outputs.</p>
7	Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use	<p>Include and embed topics of Research Assessment and Responsible Use of Research Metrics in Open Research training offerings, outreach and communication.</p> <p>Review and refresh Open Research website content annually to ensure content on Research Assessment and CoARA is up to date and easy to find.</p>
8	Exchange practices and experiences to enable	Continue to contribute to national projects and groups – (e.g. NORF, CoARA, CONUL)

	mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition	Chair or other Member(s) of Open Research Steering Group to participate in the Ireland CoARA National Chapter, ECIU CoARA Working Group and other CoARA Working Group(s)
9	Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments	Publish CoARA Action Plan on DCU news pages once approved. Review and update progress internally via DCU Research Committee and externally via channels such as Open Research Website, Research newsletter, social media.
10	Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research	<p>Continue to explore and identify emerging areas and methods for research assessment through Open Research Steering Group.</p> <p>Explore capability of new tools and systems to further develop research assessment (e.g. CRIS data in commitment 6 above).</p> <p>Publish relevant information on the Responsible Metrics section of our Open Research website.</p>